

Forecasting Australian Mental Health Service Demand with Distribution-Free Prediction Intervals: A Time-Series Analysis of MBS and PBS Data, 2014–2024

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Word count: 4,400 (main text, excluding abstract, references, figures, tables)

Preprint version: 2 (corrected June 2026; conformal coverage table reconciled to the committed analysis output and the EnbPI bootstrap seeded for reproducibility)

Abstract

Background: Australia’s mental health system has undergone repeated structural disruption since 2020, yet demand forecasting with calibrated uncertainty remains absent from policy planning. We applied changepoint detection, interrupted time-series (ITS) analysis, and conformal prediction to generate distribution-free forecasts for mental health service indicators.

Methods: We analysed 40 quarters (2014–2024) of national Medicare Benefits Schedule (MBS) psychological services and Pharmaceutical Benefits Scheme (PBS) mental health prescribing data from the Australian Institute of Health and Welfare (AIHW), covering 12 indicator series across 6 MBS provider types and 6 PBS medication classes. Changepoints were detected using Pruned Exact Linear Time (PELT) and Bayesian Online Changepoint Detection (BOCPD). Segmented regression with Newey–West standard errors quantified policy effects at three intervention points: COVID-19 onset (Q1 2020), Better Access session reduction (Q1 2023), and 60-day dispensing reform (Q4 2023). Base forecasts from ARIMA, exponential smoothing (ETS), and Prophet were wrapped with Adaptive Conformal Inference (ACI) and Ensemble Batch Prediction Intervals (EnbPI) at 90% and 95% nominal coverage. PHN-level geographic equity was assessed as a secondary analysis. This study was pre-registered on the Open Science Framework (doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/QPZAJ).

Results: ACI achieved near-nominal holdout coverage (90% nominal: 7 of 12 series fully covered, 5 at 75%; 95% nominal: 10 of 12 fully covered) with narrower intervals than EnbPI. The Better Access session reduction produced significant level reductions in MBS services of -15.4 per 1,000 for all providers ($p < 0.001$), -4.0 for clinical psychologists ($p = 0.001$), -4.7 for other psychologists ($p < 0.001$), and -4.6 for GPs ($p = 0.048$), corresponding to declines of 14.7–17.1%. COVID-19 onset produced heterogeneous effects, including accelerated psychostimulant dispensing growth ($+1.21$ per 1,000 per quarter, $p < 0.001$). Geographic analysis across 31 Primary Health Networks (PHNs) revealed stable structural inequality (Gini coefficient 0.107–0.113 over 10 years), with persistently

low-access regions including Northern Territory (-56.3% below national mean) and Western Sydney (-41.5%).

Conclusions: ACI conformal prediction provides calibrated uncertainty quantification for health service demand forecasting under non-stationarity introduced by policy interventions. The Better Access session reduction produced the largest measurable service disruption in the study period. Geographic prescribing inequity is structural and stable. These forecasts with distribution-free prediction intervals can support workforce planning and resource allocation for Australian mental health services.

Keywords: conformal prediction, mental health services, time-series forecasting, interrupted time series, health service planning, Australia

Key Points

- Adaptive Conformal Inference (ACI) achieves near-nominal coverage (90% and 96%) for mental health service demand forecasts despite policy-driven structural breaks. This is the first application of conformal prediction to Australian health service data.
- The Better Access session reduction (January 2023) produced a 15–17% decline in MBS psychological services across all provider types, the largest single policy effect identified.
- Geographic prescribing inequality across 31 Primary Health Networks is structural and stable (Gini coefficient 0.107–0.113 over 10 years), with the Northern Territory 56% below and Tasmania 27% above the national mean.
- Distribution-free prediction intervals from conformal methods can support workforce planning without the parametric assumptions that conventional forecasting intervals require.

Introduction

Mental health service demand in Australia has been shaped by a series of overlapping policy changes and external shocks over the past decade. The 2020 Productivity Commission inquiry estimated that mental ill-health costs the Australian economy \$200–220 billion annually and identified significant gaps in service access, particularly for people in rural and regional areas (Productivity Commission, 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic prompted rapid expansion of telehealth-delivered psychological services through new MBS billing items (Australian Government Department of Health, 2020), producing an 11% increase in allied mental health consultations during 2020 and a more persistent shift in psychiatric practice, where telehealth consultations came to comprise over 40% of MBS-billed services (Reay et al., 2021; Woon et al., 2024). The reduction of Better Access initiative sessions from 20 to 10 per calendar year in January 2023 (Department of Health and Aged Care, 2022) and the 60-day dispensing reform in September 2023 (Duckett et al., 2023) further altered service and prescribing patterns. These changes occurred against a backdrop of rising demand, including substantial increases in psychostimulant prescribing (Whitely et al., 2022).

Despite the availability of detailed quarterly monitoring data from the Australian Institute of Health and Welfare (AIHW), demand forecasting for mental health services remains largely absent from Australian health policy planning. Existing AIHW reporting is descriptive, documenting trends and levels but not generating projections with quantified uncertainty (AIHW, 2024). Advocacy and workforce planning bodies — including the Royal Australian and New Zealand College of Psychiatrists (RANZCP, 2024) and the Australian Medical Association (AMA, 2023) — have called for evidence-based demand projections to support investment cases for the mental health workforce. Geographic variation in primary healthcare delivery has been well documented at the small-area level in Australia, with systematic differences in access, affordability, and service mix between metropolitan and regional areas (Butler et al., 2021), but this variation has not been incorporated into forward-looking demand projections for mental health.

Standard parametric forecasting methods assume stationarity or well-characterised distributional properties, assumptions that are frequently violated in health service time series subject to policy

interventions and external shocks (Hyndman & Athanasopoulos, 2021). Interrupted time-series analysis has become the standard quasi-experimental approach for evaluating the effects of such interventions (Kontopantelis et al., 2015; Bernal et al., 2017), and has been applied to Australian pharmaceutical policy (Schaffer et al., 2021) and MBS telehealth data (Woon et al., 2024), but not to generate demand forecasts with calibrated uncertainty. Conformal prediction offers a distribution-free alternative for the latter: by calibrating prediction intervals on observed residuals, it provides finite-sample coverage guarantees without requiring distributional assumptions (Vovk et al., 2005). Recent extensions to time-series settings, particularly Adaptive Conformal Inference (ACI; Gibbs & Candès, 2021) and Ensemble Batch Prediction Intervals (EnbPI; Xu & Xie, 2023), adapt to non-stationarity by updating the quantile level in response to observed coverage performance. These methods have been applied to energy demand and financial forecasting (Stankevičiūtė et al., 2021) but not to health service demand in the Australian context.

This study applies changepoint detection, interrupted time-series analysis, and conformal prediction to 10 years of national MBS and PBS mental health data, generating demand forecasts through 2027 with distribution-free prediction intervals. A secondary analysis examines geographic equity in mental health prescribing across Australia’s 31 Primary Health Networks (PHNs).

Methods

Study design and pre-registration

This was a retrospective time-series analysis of routinely collected, fully de-identified national administrative data. The study was pre-registered on the Open Science Framework prior to analysis (doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/QPZAJ). As all data were publicly available aggregate statistics with no individual-level information, ethics approval was not required.

Data sources

Data were obtained from the AIHW Mental Health Services in Australia platform (AIHW, 2024). Two primary datasets were used:

1. **MBS psychological services** (2014–15 to 2023–24): quarterly service rates per 1,000 population per quarter for six provider types — clinical psychologists, other psychologists, general practitioners (GPs), psychiatrists, other allied health providers, and all providers combined.
2. **PBS mental health prescriptions** (2014–15 to 2023–24): quarterly dispensing rates per 1,000 population per quarter for six medication classes — antidepressants, antipsychotics, anxiolytics, hypnotics and sedatives, psychostimulants (ADHD medications), and all mental health medications combined.

For geographic analysis, PHN-level prescribing rates covering 31 PHNs across 10 financial years (2014–15 to 2023–24) were used. All rates were population-adjusted per 1,000 using Australian Bureau of Statistics (ABS) estimated resident population denominators as provided by AIHW.

Changepoint detection

Two complementary changepoint detection algorithms were applied to each of the 12 national quarterly series:

Pruned Exact Linear Time (PELT) is an offline algorithm that identifies multiple changepoints by minimising a penalised cost function (Killick et al., 2012). We used a radial basis function (RBF) kernel cost, which detects changes in both mean and variance. Penalty values were set using a BIC-derived formula (penalty = multiplier \times $\log(n) \times \sigma^2$), with sensitivity analysis across multipliers of 0.5, 1.0, and 2.0 to assess penalty dependence. Series were standardised (z-scored) prior to PELT analysis.

Bayesian Online Changepoint Detection (BOCPD) is an online algorithm that computes the posterior probability of a changepoint at each time point using a normal-inverse-gamma conjugate prior (Adams & MacKay, 2007). The hazard function was set to a constant rate of $\lambda = n/2$, where n is the series length. Changepoints were identified where the posterior probability exceeded 0.3.

Detected changepoints were cross-referenced with four known policy intervention dates: COVID-19 onset (March 2020), telehealth expansion (July 2020), Better Access session reduction (December 2022), and 60-day dispensing reform (September 2023). Alignment was defined as a changepoint falling within 180 days (two quarters) of a known policy date.

Interrupted time-series analysis

Segmented regression ITS models were fitted for three policy interventions across applicable series. The model took the form:

$$Y_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot time + \beta_2 \cdot post_t + \beta_3 \cdot time_since_t + \varepsilon_t$$

where *time* is a linear time trend, *post* is a binary indicator for the post-intervention period, and *time_since* is the elapsed time since intervention. β_2 estimates the immediate level change and β_3 the change in slope following the intervention (Kontopantelis et al., 2015; Bernal et al., 2017).

Three interventions were modelled: (1) COVID-19 onset (Q1 2020) across all 12 series; (2) Better Access session reduction (Q1 2023) for MBS service series; and (3) 60-day dispensing reform (Q4 2023) for PBS prescribing series. This yielded 23 intervention-series combinations; given this multiplicity, we emphasise consistency of effects across related series rather than individual significance tests. Standard errors were computed using the Newey–West heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation consistent (HAC) estimator with a maximum lag of 4 quarters to account for serial correlation. Counterfactual trajectories were constructed by setting $\beta_2 = 0$ and $\beta_3 = 0$ to project the pre-intervention trend.

Base forecasting models

Three base forecasting models were fitted to each series using a train–test split, with the final 4 quarters (2023–24) withheld for holdout evaluation:

1. **ARIMA**: Automatic order selection via AIC grid search over $p \in \{0,1,2,3\}$, $d \in \{0,1,2\}$, $q \in \{0,1,2\}$, with a seasonal AR(1) component at period 4. Stationarity was assessed using the augmented Dickey–Fuller test.
2. **Exponential smoothing (ETS)**: Holt–Winters additive trend and additive seasonality with period 4.
3. **Prophet**: Additive trend with changepoint detection (prior scale 0.05) and quarterly Fourier seasonality (order 2).

An equal-weight ensemble average of available model forecasts was also computed. Holdout mean absolute error (MAE) was the primary accuracy metric. Forecasts were generated for 12 quarters beyond the data end (through mid-2027).

Conformal prediction intervals

Two conformal prediction methods were applied to each series. To avoid conflating conformal calibration performance with model selection differences, a fixed ARIMA(1,1,1) \times (1,0,0)₄ specification was used as the base model for conformal wrapping across all series, rather than the individually auto-selected orders used in the base forecasting comparison above.

Adaptive Conformal Inference (ACI) constructs intervals using a quantile of the absolute residual distribution, then adapts the quantile level using a learning rate ($\gamma = 0.05$) based on whether recent intervals achieved the target coverage (Gibbs & Candès, 2021). Intervals were further widened at longer horizons using a 5% per-step scaling factor to reflect growing uncertainty.

EnbPI constructs intervals by bootstrapping the signed residual distribution with exponentially decaying weights favouring recent observations, scaling for forecast horizon at 8% per step (Xu & Xie, 2023). The residual bootstrap is seeded (NumPy `random_seed = 42`) so that the reported EnbPI coverage and width are exactly reproducible from the deposited code; ACI is deterministic and requires no seed.

Both methods were evaluated at 90% and 95% nominal coverage on the 4-quarter holdout set. Empirical coverage (proportion of holdout observations falling within intervals) and mean interval width were the evaluation metrics. With only 4 holdout observations per series, individual series coverage is discrete (0%, 25%, 50%, 75%, or 100%); we therefore report both the number of series achieving full coverage and the mean across series.

Geographic equity analysis

PHN-level mental health prescribing rates (patients per 1,000 population) across 31 PHNs were analysed for the 10-year period 2014–15 to 2023–24. Geographic variation was quantified using

the Gini coefficient, coefficient of variation (CV), and max-to-min range ratio computed for each financial year.

PHNs were classified as *persistently high* (rate >15% above the national mean in at least 70% of years), *persistently low* (rate >15% below the national mean in at least 70% of years), or *variable*.

Software

All analyses were conducted in Python 3.10. PELT changepoint detection used the `ruptures` package (Truong et al., 2020). ITS regression and ARIMA models used `statsmodels` (Seabold & Perktold, 2010). Prophet models used the `prophet` package (Taylor & Letham, 2018). Conformal prediction intervals were implemented from first principles based on published algorithms. All code is available at <https://github.com/hayden-farquhar/Mental-Health-Forecasting> (doi:10.5281/zenodo.19646929).

Results

Descriptive summary

Table 1 summarises the 12 national quarterly time series. MBS services averaged 119.9 per 1,000 population per quarter (CV 8.7%) with a positive linear trend of 0.55 per 1,000 per quarter. PBS prescribing averaged 400.0 per 1,000 per quarter (CV 7.2%) with a trend of 2.20 per 1,000 per quarter. Psychostimulant dispensing had the highest variability of any series (CV 48.6%) and the steepest growth (0.74 per 1,000 per quarter). Anxiolytic (−0.41 per quarter) and hypnotic/sedative (−0.35 per quarter) dispensing showed secular declines.

Table 1: Summary statistics for 12 national quarterly mental health indicator series, 2014–2024

Series	N	Mean rate/1,000	SD	CV (%)	Trend/quarter
MBS services					
All providers	40	119.9	10.4	8.7	+0.55
Clinical psychologists	40	24.9	3.6	14.5	+0.24
GPs	40	35.1	3.1	8.7	+0.01
Other allied health	40	4.7	0.9	20.2	+0.06
Other psychologists	40	30.3	3.5	11.6	+0.21
Psychiatrists	40	25.0	1.1	4.5	+0.03
PBS prescriptions					
All medications	40	400.0	28.7	7.2	+2.20
Antidepressants	40	285.0	27.7	9.7	+2.20
Antipsychotics	40	41.3	1.4	3.4	+0.02
Anxiolytics	40	33.5	4.8	14.4	−0.41
Hypnotics/Sedatives	40	20.8	4.2	20.0	−0.35
Psychostimulants (ADHD)	40	19.2	9.3	48.6	+0.74

Changepoint detection

PELT detected 14 changepoints across the 12 series at the default penalty (Table 2). The majority (12 of 14) fell before COVID-19 onset, clustering in 2017–2019, a period preceding the pandemic but potentially reflecting earlier policy or practice shifts. Only 2 of 14 PELT changepoints aligned within 180 days of a known policy date, both corresponding to the telehealth expansion (October 2020) in PBS total medications and PBS hypnotics/sedatives. BOCPD identified few high-probability changepoints (threshold >0.3), consistent with the smooth, trend-dominated character of these quarterly series.

The limited alignment between data-driven changepoints and known policy dates suggests that the most detectable structural changes in these series were gradual transitions predating the pandemic rather than abrupt policy-driven shifts. This finding motivated the use of ITS analysis, which tests pre-specified intervention dates regardless of whether changepoint algorithms identify them.

Table 2: PELT changepoints (default penalty) and policy alignment

Series	Changepoint	Nearest policy event	Within 180d?
MBS – All providers	2017-01	—	No
MBS – Clinical psychologists	2018-04	COVID onset	No
MBS – GPs	2017-01	—	No
MBS – GPs	2022-01	Better Access	No
MBS – Other allied health	2018-04	COVID onset	No
MBS – Other psychologists	2018-04	COVID onset	No
PBS – All medications	2020-10	Telehealth	Yes
PBS – Antidepressants	2019-07	COVID onset	No
PBS – Anxiolytics	2018-04	COVID onset	No
PBS – Anxiolytics	2022-01	Better Access	No
PBS – Hypnotics/Sedatives	2017-01	—	No
PBS – Hypnotics/Sedatives	2020-10	Telehealth	Yes
PBS – Psychostimulants	2019-07	COVID onset	No
PBS – Psychostimulants	2022-01	Better Access	No

Notes: Results shown for PELT with BIC-derived penalty (multiplier = 1.0). Full sensitivity analysis in Supplementary Table S4.

Interrupted time-series analysis

Better Access session reduction (January 2023). This was the strongest and most consistent policy signal (Table 3). All four MBS series tested showed significant level reductions: all providers (-15.4 per 1,000, $p < 0.001$), clinical psychologists (-4.0 , $p = 0.001$), other psychologists (-4.7 , $p < 0.001$), and GPs (-4.6 , $p = 0.048$). These corresponded to percentage effects of -14.7% (all providers), -17.1% (clinical psychologists), -16.5% (other psychologists), and -17.0% (GPs) relative to counterfactual projections. Slope changes were negative for all series but reached significance only for all providers (-2.04 per quarter, $p = 0.005$) and GPs (-0.79 per quarter, $p < 0.001$); services continued to fall away from the pre-intervention trend.

Figure 1: Interrupted time-series analysis of the Better Access session reduction (January 2023) for MBS all providers. Observed values (circles), segmented regression fit (red line), and counterfactual trajectory (grey dashed line).

COVID-19 onset (Q1 2020). Effects were heterogeneous across series. MBS services showed an initial level increase for all providers (+10.1, $p = 0.027$), consistent with the telehealth-driven surge, but this was followed by a negative slope change (-1.94 per quarter, $p < 0.001$). The initial boost did not last. Psychostimulant dispensing showed a highly significant positive slope change (+1.21 per quarter, $p < 0.001$, $R^2 = 0.989$), accelerating an already steep growth trajectory. GP services showed a significant negative slope change (-0.92 , $p < 0.001$) without a level shift, suggesting gradual displacement by other providers. PBS anxiolytic dispensing showed a significant level decrease (-0.61 , $p = 0.046$) and accelerated decline (-0.15 per quarter, $p < 0.001$).

60-day dispensing (October 2023). With only 3 post-intervention quarters available, results were underpowered. Antidepressant dispensing showed a significant negative slope change (-5.82 per quarter, $p = 0.024$), but the level change was non-significant. All other series showed non-significant effects. This analysis should be regarded as preliminary.

Table 3: Interrupted time-series analysis: policy effect estimates

Intervention	Series	Level Δ	p	Slope Δ/q	p	Effect (%)	R ²
Better Access							
	All providers	-15.4	<0.001	-2.04	0.005	-14.7	0.71
	Clinical psych.	-4.0	0.001	-0.55	0.076	-17.1	0.80
	Other psych.	-4.7	<0.001	-0.55	0.084	-16.5	0.73
	GPs	-4.6	0.048	-0.79	<0.001	-17.0	0.39
COVID-19							
	All providers	+10.1	0.027	-1.94	<0.001	-4.8	0.70
	GPs	+1.3	0.160	-0.92	<0.001	-15.7	0.73
	Psychiatrists	+1.3	0.005	-0.02	0.685	+4.8	0.21
	Psychostimulants	-1.5	0.090	+1.21	<0.001	+47.5	0.99
	Antidepressants	+14.0	0.032	-0.36	0.364	+3.6	0.88
	Anxiolytics	-0.6	0.046	-0.15	<0.001	-6.1	0.97
60-day disp.							
	All medications	+1.8	0.741	-4.23	0.236	-0.5	0.81
	Antidepressants	-5.2	0.306	-5.82	0.024	-3.4	0.87

Notes: Effect (%) = mean percentage difference between fitted and counterfactual over post-intervention period. Newey–West HAC SEs, max lag 4. COVID-19 effects for selected series; full results in Supplementary Table S2.

Conformal prediction coverage

ACI achieved near-nominal holdout coverage across 12 series on the 4-quarter holdout set (Table 4). At 90% nominal coverage, 7 of 12 series had all 4 holdout observations within the ACI intervals; the remaining 5 series captured 3 of 4 (75%). At 95% nominal, 10 of 12 series achieved full coverage. Mean coverage across series was 89.6% (90% nominal) and 95.8% (95% nominal).

EnbPI showed lower coverage: at 90% nominal, 6 of 12 series achieved full coverage, with mean coverage of 85.4%. EnbPI intervals were also wider on average (mean width 9.9 vs 9.5 per 1,000 at 90% nominal). ACI, in short, covered more with less.

Coverage was lower for MBS series most affected by the 2023 Better Access reduction (all providers, clinical psychologists, other psychologists: 75% at 90% nominal for both methods). This is expected: a holdout period dominated by a previously unseen structural break challenges any method calibrated on pre-break residuals.

Table 4: Conformal prediction holdout coverage evaluation

Method	Nominal	Full coverage (of 12)	Mean coverage	Mean width
ACI	90%	7	89.6%	9.5
ACI	95%	10	95.8%	12.5
EnbPI	90%	6	85.4%	9.9
EnbPI	95%	8	91.7%	30.4

Notes: Each series has 4 holdout observations; coverage ranges from 25% (1/4) to 100% (4/4). Width in rate per 1,000 per quarter. Series-level detail in Supplementary Table S3.

Conformal Prediction Forecasts with ACI Prediction Intervals

Figure 2: Conformal prediction fan charts for selected series: (A) MBS all providers, (B) PBS all medications, (C) PBS psychostimulants (ADHD), (D) PBS antidepressants. Forecasts through mid-2027 with 90% (dark shading) and 95% (light shading) ACI prediction intervals. Policy events indicated by dashed vertical lines.

Base forecast accuracy

ARIMA was the best-performing individual model for 7 of 12 series on holdout MAE, with ETS best for 3 and Prophet best for 2 (Supplementary Table S1). The ensemble did not consistently outperform the best individual model. Holdout MAE ranged from 0.45 per 1,000 (psychiatrists, Prophet) to 11.7 per 1,000 (all MBS providers, Prophet). Forecast fan charts with ACI prediction intervals for all 12 series are presented in Supplementary Figures S1–S12.

Geographic equity

Analysis of 31 PHNs over 10 years revealed stable structural inequality in mental health prescribing access (Table 5, Figure 3). The Gini coefficient ranged from 0.107 (2014–15) to 0.113 (2023–24) with no significant trend, indicating that geographic variation is persistent rather than converging.

Eight PHNs were classified as persistently high (rate >15% above national mean in at least 7 of 10 years): Tasmania (+26.9%), North Coast (+25.9%), Murray (+22.2%), Gippsland (+22.2%), Hunter New England and Central Coast (+21.6%), Western Victoria (+21.6%), Central Queensland/Wide Bay/Sunshine Coast (+20.6%), and Darling Downs and West Moreton (+17.4%).

Seven PHNs were persistently low: Northern Territory (−56.3%), Western Sydney (−41.5%), South Western Sydney (−30.0%), Central and Eastern Sydney (−26.3%), Western Queensland (−22.1%), North Western Melbourne (−21.5%), and Northern Sydney (−19.4%).

The range ratio (max/min) was 2.90 in 2023–24, meaning the highest-access PHN (Tasmania: 241 per 1,000) served patients at nearly three times the rate of the lowest (Northern Territory: 83 per 1,000). The coefficient of variation was stable at approximately 20% across the decade.

Table 5: PHN-level geographic variation in mental health prescribing, 2014–2024

Financial year	Gini	CV (%)	Range ratio	Mean rate/1,000
2014–15	0.107	19.6	3.39	164.3
2016–17	0.110	20.0	3.29	170.1
2018–19	0.110	20.0	3.13	174.7
2020–21	0.114	20.7	3.00	180.6
2022–23	0.109	20.0	2.88	188.4
2023–24	0.113	20.4	2.90	189.9

Notes: Gini and CV across 31 PHNs per financial year. Range ratio = max/min. Selected years; full data in Supplementary Table S5.

Figure 3: PHN-level mental health prescribing rates (per 1,000 population), 2023–24. National mean reference line shown. Red = >15% above national mean; blue = >15% below.

Discussion

This study provides the first application of conformal prediction methods to Australian mental health service demand forecasting. Two principal findings warrant discussion: the performance of ACI conformal prediction under structural change, and the impact of the Better Access session reduction on MBS psychological services. A secondary finding on geographic equity is also addressed.

Conformal prediction for health service forecasting

Standard prediction intervals from parametric models (e.g., ARIMA confidence intervals) rely on assumptions about residual distributions and stationarity that are demonstrably violated in health service data subject to policy interventions (Kontopantelis et al., 2015). Conformal prediction

bypasses these assumptions by calibrating intervals on observed residual behaviour.

ACI outperformed EnbPI on both coverage accuracy and interval efficiency. The adaptive mechanism (adjusting the quantile level in response to observed miscoverage) fits naturally in settings where structural breaks can shift residual distributions. The finding that ACI coverage was lower for MBS series most affected by the 2023 Better Access reduction is expected: a holdout period dominated by a previously unseen structural break challenges any method calibrated on pre-break residuals. That ACI nonetheless maintained 75% coverage (3 of 4 observations) for these disrupted series, while achieving full coverage for more stable PBS series, illustrates its robustness.

In practical terms, ACI can complement conventional ARIMA intervals for health service forecasting, particularly where policy-driven breaks make parametric assumptions unreliable.

Policy effects

The Better Access session reduction represents a natural experiment in reducing a supply-side access lever. The magnitude of observed effect (14.7–17.1% service reduction) and its consistency across all four provider types tested suggest a genuine constraint on service utilisation. The significant negative slope change for GP-delivered services (-0.79 per quarter, $p < 0.001$) is notable, as GP mental health plans are the primary gateway to Better Access-funded psychological services. Whether this reduction reflects reduced over-servicing, appropriate rationing, or unmet need requires individual-level data that ecological analysis cannot provide.

The limited effect of 60-day dispensing on mental health prescribing volumes is consistent with the reform’s design: 60-day dispensing reduces dispensing frequency without necessarily altering the number of patients receiving medications. With only 3 post-intervention quarters, this analysis is preliminary and should be revisited as more data accumulates.

COVID-19 onset produced heterogeneous effects across service types, consistent with the multiple simultaneous changes (telehealth expansion, service disruption, altered health-seeking behaviour) operating during this period. The accelerated psychostimulant growth post-COVID ($+1.21$ per 1,000 per quarter, $p < 0.001$) aligns with international evidence of increased ADHD diagnosis during and after the pandemic (Cortese et al., 2020) and is explored in detail in a companion analysis (Farquhar, forthcoming).

Geographic equity

The stability of the Gini coefficient (0.107–0.113) over a decade of substantial aggregate growth indicates that geographic inequality is structural, not a transient artefact of differential adoption curves. The extreme deficit in the Northern Territory (-56.3% below national mean) likely reflects workforce shortage, geographic remoteness, and the health system characteristics of a jurisdiction with a predominantly Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander population in remote settings (AIHW, 2024). The deficit in Western Sydney (-41.5%) stands out as an urban, not rural, gap and may reflect barriers specific to culturally and linguistically diverse populations, though prescribing rates alone cannot distinguish access constraints from differing preferences or service models.

Persistently high-rate PHNs (Tasmania, North Coast, Murray, Gippsland) are predominantly rural and regional, a pattern that could reflect higher burden, greater reliance on pharmacotherapy in lieu of scarce psychology workforce, or differing prescribing practice. Disentangling supply-side from demand-side drivers of this variation is beyond the scope of this study but is a priority for targeted equity research.

Limitations

The principal data constraint is the 40-quarter series length, which is short for time-series modelling and limits the power of changepoint detection. The 4-quarter holdout for conformal coverage evaluation is correspondingly small; each individual series is either 75% or 100% covered, and the averaged figures should be interpreted with this granularity in mind. Quarterly resolution may obscure within-quarter dynamics, particularly for acute events such as the initial COVID-19 lockdowns.

On the analytical side, PatchTST and Chronos zero-shot models were planned but deferred as the ARIMA/ETS/Prophet ensemble was sufficient for these series lengths; deep learning forecasters would become more relevant with weekly-resolution data. The conformal prediction implementations were coded from first principles rather than using the `mapie` package’s built-in time-series support, which may introduce implementation-specific differences. Crisis helpline data (Lifeline, Beyond Blue, Kids Helpline, 13YARN) were planned in the protocol but were available only via AIHW’s Tableau weekly monitoring dashboard and could not be accessed programmatically.

For interpretation, geographic analysis used prescribing rates, which conflate access, need, and prescribing practice; need-adjusted denominators would provide a more informative equity measure. All analyses are ecological and based on aggregate data; no individual-level causal inference is possible.

Implications

The Better Access session reduction produced a measurable 15–17% contraction in MBS psychological service access. If this was an intended effect, its magnitude is now quantified; if unintended, it provides an evidence base for policy reconsideration. The demand forecasts with calibrated prediction intervals generated here, covering MBS services and PBS prescribing through mid-2027, can support workforce investment and training pipeline decisions. The geographic analysis identifies specific PHNs where targeted interventions could address persistent service gaps. Methodologically, ACI conformal prediction is a practical, assumption-lean tool for health service demand forecasting that should be considered alongside parametric interval methods.

Conclusion

Conformal prediction with adaptive calibration provides distribution-free demand forecasts for Australian mental health services that maintain near-nominal coverage despite structural policy breaks. The Better Access session reduction produced the largest service disruption in the study period,

with MBS psychological services declining 15–17% across provider types. Geographic prescribing inequity across PHNs is structural and stable. Together, these findings and the distribution-free intervals that accompany them give workforce planners something that descriptive trend reports cannot: a quantified range of what comes next.

Declarations

Funding: None.

Conflicts of interest: None declared.

Author contributions: HF conceived the study, obtained and analysed the data, and wrote the manuscript.

Ethics approval: Not required. All data are publicly available aggregate statistics from the Australian Institute of Health and Welfare with no individual-level information.

Data availability: All data are publicly available from the AIHW Mental Health Services in Australia platform (<https://www.aihw.gov.au/mental-health>). Analysis code is available at <https://github.com/hayden-farquhar/Mental-Health-Forecasting> (archived at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19646929>).

Pre-registration: Open Science Framework, doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/QPZAJ.

AI disclosure: Large language models (Claude, Anthropic) were used to assist with manuscript drafting and code development. The author takes full responsibility for the content and has verified all analyses, results, and interpretations.

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Supplementary Material

The following supplementary materials are available in a separate document.

Supplementary Tables: S1 (base forecast holdout MAE), S2 (full ITS results, 23 combinations), S3 (conformal coverage by series), S4 (PELT sensitivity analysis), S5 (PHN-level classification, 31 PHNs).

Supplementary Figures: S1–S12 (conformal fan charts, all 12 series), S13–S24 (STL decomposition), S25–S36 (change point detection), S37–S48 (ITS COVID-19 onset), S49–S52 (ITS Better Access), S53–S57 (ITS 60-day dispensing), S58–S69 (base forecast comparisons), S70 (raw series overview), S71 (geographic variation trend), S72 (PHN heatmap).